

CHEMICAL SCIENCES

THE MOBILE FORMS OF HEAVY METALS IN SOILS OF RAILWAY STATIONS OF GEORGIA

*Akhalbedashvili L.,
Todoradze G.,
Kvatashidze R.,
Loria N.,
Gagniashvili N.,
Janashvili N.,
Jalaghania S.,
Surguladze R.,
Ukleba M.*

Ivane Javakhishvili Tbilisi State University Alexandre Tvalchrelidze Caucasian Institute of Mineral Resources, Tbilisi, Georgia

ABSTRACT

Based on previously obtained results of determining the gross content of heavy metals in the soils of railway stations in the Tbilisi-Borjomi section, the chemical forms of their existence in the soil, in particular, mobile forms of HMs, were studied. The content of mobile forms of metals extracted by an ammonium acetate buffer solution with pH = 4.8 is determined primarily by the type of soil, its composition and physicochemical principles, while the pattern remains, expressed in an increase in the number of mobile compounds of Cd, Pb and Zn in acidic soil.

Keywords: heavy metals, mobile forms, railway stations.

Introduction

The first works on the study of technogenic contamination of soils with heavy metals appeared back in the 60-70s of the 20th century. Since then, the scale of human impact on the environment has sharply increased, the number of chemical elements and substances polluting the soil has increased, methods of chemical analysis have improved, and ideas about the behavior of pollutants in the soil have changed [1-3].

Aerotechnogenic contamination of soils with heavy metals (HM) has long become a common phenomenon of modern life and has multi-element in nature.

The general soil contamination is characterized by the gross amount of heavy metal.

The availability of elements for plants is determined by their mobile forms. Therefore, the content of solid metals in liquid forms of soil is the most important indicator characterizing the sanitary and hygienic situation and determining the need for ameliorative detoxification measures.

Depending on the extractant used, different amounts of the mobile form of the heavy metal are extracted, which with a certain convention can be considered accessible to plants. To extract mobile forms of heavy metals, various chemical compounds with different extracting powers are used:

acids, salts, buffer solutions and water. The most common extractants are water, 1N HCl and ammonium acetate buffer with pH 4.8.

The description of problem

At present, insufficient experimental material has been accumulated to characterize the dependence of the content of heavy metals in plants extracted by various chemical solutions on their concentration in the soil. There are over 40 heavy metals in total. Pb, Cd, Zn, Hg, As and Cu are considered priority pollutants, since their

technogenic accumulation in the environment occurs at a very high rate.

These elements have a high affinity for physiologically important organic compounds. Their excessive amounts in the body of living beings disrupt all metabolic processes and lead to serious diseases in humans and animals.

At the same time, many of the heavy elements (Co, Cu, Zn, Se, Mn) are quite widely used in national economic production (especially in agriculture, medicine, etc.) under the name microelements. It denotes a group of chemical elements that are found in natural objects in very small quantities - less than 0.01%, usually 10⁻³-10⁻¹²%.

Formally, the identification is based on their prevalence in nature, which varies significantly for different natural environments and objects (lithosphere, pedosphere, bottom sediments, hydrosphere, plants, animals, etc.). The gross content of HM is one of the main indicators of chemical composition used in the study of chemical contamination of soils. But studying only the gross content of HM in soils is insufficient.

Previously, we showed [4] that the soils of railway stations in the Tbilisi-Borjomi section are very heavily polluted with heavy metals; the values of gross HM contents and the dependence of the content on the profile depth are given. The purpose of this work is to study the chemical forms of metals in the soil of railway stations in the same section of the Georgian railway, and their dependence from outside conditions.

There are several methods for studying the forms of chemical elements, but the most commonly used is sequential chemical extraction. Popular extraction schemes include Tessier, BCR, Miller, McLaren-Crawford schemes [5-10].

Moreover, the presence of various forms of HM compounds, differing both in mobility and in the mechanisms of fixation in the soil, is of great importance,

determines the degree of their environmental hazard and requires detailed study. In this regard, soil scientists pay much attention to the study of the types and forms of heavy metals. But these forms are difficult to identify even on models.

The main reasons for the difficulties are the low concentration of metals for traditional crystallographic equipment, the influence of coexisting minerals, difficulties in identifying carrier minerals, and the variety of sorption mechanisms.

As a result of treating the soil with these solutions, ions and compounds of heavy metals pass into them, which can be combined into one fraction.

The data obtained during fractionation allows:

1. Assess and separate the anthropogenic and natural components of the content of heavy metals in the soil.

2. Assess the mobility of heavy metals and the sequential fractionation of HM compounds in soils, including sequential treatment of one sample of soil with specially selected extracting solutions, allows us to obtain a very complete picture of the distribution of heavy metals by form of compounds. The extracting solutions used have a predominant effect either on a separate group of soil components (for example, non-silicate iron compounds), or on a certain type of connection of metal ions with solid-phase soil components (for example, the displacement of exchangeable cations from the soil absorption complex).

Possibility of their strong fixation in the soil.

When soils are exposed to solutions of strong acids exhibiting the properties of oxidizing agents (nitric acid), or a mixture of acid with a strong oxidizing agent - $\text{HNO}_3 + \text{H}_2\text{O}_2$, $\text{HNO}_3 + \text{HClO}_4$, $\text{HNO}_3 + \text{HCl}$ ("aqua regia"), soil components are destroyed during microwave irradiation. Most metal ions go into solution. The strongly acidic reaction of the medium prevents secondary precipitation and sorption of metals by the remaining solid-phase components in the system, mainly represented by silicon and aluminum compounds. The total concentration of matrix components in the solution turns out to be many times lower than during soil decomposition by fusion or complete acid decomposition.

The non-recoverable part of HM in background soils is represented by the most stable compounds in the composition of primary minerals; in contaminated soils, some of the most chemically stable technogenic particles are added to them. Under normal conditions, these compounds cannot participate in soil, geochemical and biological processes (except for mechanical movement in the composition of the particles containing them), and, thus, do not play a role in studying the mobility and potential toxicity of HM in soil.

Materials and methods

The study of technogenic soil pollution was carried out in the territories of railway stations in Georgian cities from Tbilisi to Borjomi.

To study the completeness of extraction of HM into solution by various acid mixtures, certified standard samples of soils were used.

Acid decomposition of standard samples was carried out in a Microwave Pressure Digestion Labstation

MWS-3, BERGHOF. Strong acid 1N HNO_3 , ammonium acetate buffer solution with $\text{pH} = 4.8$ and water were used as extractants.

Comparing the results obtained with the certified content of the elements, the following patterns were identified.

Cr, Mn, Fe, Co, Ni, Cu, Zn, Pb go into solution equally well with all methods of acid decomposition. To optimize the analysis and minimize possible errors associated with excessive exposure to soil, when determining the gross content of these elements in similar soils, their microwave decomposition with HNO_3 diluted with water in a ratio of 1:1 can be recommended.

Thus, based on the results of determining the content of HM obtained using different variants of acid decomposition, it is impossible to unambiguously identify one universal method that would be easy to use and suitable for all HM.

The use of different options for microwave acid decomposition of soils should be carried out depending on the set of elements being studied. Incomplete acid digestion simplifies the digestion procedure, reduces matrix loading, reduces overall analysis time, and eliminates the use of harmful chemicals without compromising the quality of the results obtained.

As a result of soil treatment with these solutions, ions and compounds of HMs pass into them, which can be combined into one set, called a fraction or group of HM compounds.

Chemical analyses

After collection, the soil samples were homogenized, transferred to Petri dishes, and lyophilized. To determine the concentration of seven HM (Zn, Cu, Pb, Cd, Ni, Cr, and Fe) a soil subsample of 0.5 g (0.001 g accuracy) was digested with HNO_3 and HCl (1:3) in Teflon bombs in an oven (140 °C), for 4 h, approximately according to the procedure described by [11]. The solution was then evaporated to dryness and 5 mL of concentrated HNO_3 was added and evaporated. The dried residue was dissolved in 5 mL of 0.1 M HNO_3 and placed in polyethylene tubes. Dilutions of $\times 10$, $\times 100$, and $\times 1000$ were prepared and analyzed in a mass spectrometer (Perkin-Elmer AAnalyst 200). The results are presented as mg/kg d.w. (d.w. – dry weight). The measurements were replicated three times. Quality control was assured by analyzing a certified reference material and "blanks", according to the same procedure. Recoveries were in the range of 92–103%, depending on the individual metals. The precision, given as Relative Standard Deviation, was in the range of 3–5%.

Results and Discussion

The results of this work indicate that the content of acid-soluble compounds of zinc, lead, copper and cadmium, passing into the 1N HNO_3 extract, is close to their amounts contained in the soil and depends on the type of soil. This extractant extracted 75-87% Pb, 83-100% Cd and Cu, 74-94% of Zn entering the soil. The content of mobile forms of metals extracted with an ammonium acetate buffer solution with $\text{pH} = 4.8$, was also determined primarily by the type of soil, its composition and physicochemical properties, while maintaining a pattern expressed in an increase in the

number of mobile compounds of Cd, Pb and Zn in acidic soil, and the mobility of Cd and Zn is higher than that of Pb. It known that the soils that are exposed to anthropogenic impact accumulate the largest amount of Pb, Cd, Zn, Mn, Cu. So, the available literature and our experimental data indicate that the reaction of the environment in the soil greatly influences the mobility of elements.

The part of heavy metals extracted by aqueous extract is the most active fraction of compounds - aggressive and dynamic.

It is known that the pH value of the soil solution is one of the most important parameters that determine the amount of sorption of heavy metal ions by the soil.

As pH decreases, the solubility of most heavy metals increases and, consequently, their mobility in the soil solid phase-solution system increases. J. Esser, N. Bassam (1981), studying the mobility of cadmium in aerobic soil conditions, found that in the pH range 4-6, the mobility of cadmium is determined by the ionic strength of the solution; at pH above 6, sorption by manganese oxides takes on leading importance.

Soluble organic compounds, according to the authors, form only weak complexes with cadmium and affect its sorption at pH 8.

Table.

The content of heavy metals mobile forms on some railway stations of Georgia, mg/kg

Location	Zn	Ni	Cu	Cr	Cd	Pb
Borjomi	49.05	5.02	4.04	1.94	0.07	5.15
Khashuri	107.91	5.82	4.49	2.23	0.35	49.51
Kareli	127.01	5.72	8.31	2.52	0.12	14.83
Gori	102.53	11.50	6.05	3.73	0.18	7.57
Mckheta	102.41	7.83	5.53	3.06	0.20	11.62
Tbilisi	72.51	0.53	0.40	No det.	No det.	0.66
MPC*	23	4	3	6	0.5-1	6

MPC*– Maximal Permissible Concentration

The most mobile and accessible part of heavy metal compounds in the soil for plants is their content in the soil solution. The amount of metal ions entering the soil solution determines the toxicity of a specific element in the soil [12].

The state of equilibrium in the solid phase - solution system determines sorption processes, the nature and direction of which depend on the properties and composition of the soil.

It was found that most of the studied elements in the soils of the background plot are inactive. But in the territories adjacent to industrial facilities, in the upper part of the humus horizon, the content of Cu, Zn, Cd in the oxidized and reduced fractions, as well as the fraction of crystalline Fe hydroxides, increases.

The content of mobile forms of metals extracted by an ammonium acetate buffer solution with pH = 4.8 is also determined primarily by the type of soil, its composition and physicochemical properties, while the pattern remains, expressed in an increase in the number of mobile compounds of Cd, Pb and Zn in acidic soil.

Conclusion

It was found that most of the studied elements in the soils of the background plot are inactive. But in areas adjacent to industrial facilities, in the upper part of the humus horizon, the content of Cu, Zn, Cd in the oxidizable and reduced fractions, as well as the group of crystalline Fe hydroxides, increases. The content of mobile forms of metals extracted by an ammonium acetate buffer solution with pH = 4.8 is determined primarily by the type of soil, its composition and physicochemical principles, while a pattern is given that is expressed in an increase in the number of mobile compounds of Cd, Pb and Zn in acidic soil.

References

1. J. Xu, C. Liu, P.-C. Hsu, J. Zhao, T. Wu, J. Tang, K. Liu, Y. Cui., (2019). Remediation of heavy metal contaminated soil by asymmetrical alternating current electrochemistry, *Nat. Commun.*, 10 (1), pp. 1-8;
2. G. Tóth, T. Hermann, M.R. Da Silva, L.J.E.I. Montanarella. (2016) Heavy metals in agricultural soils of the European Union with implications for food safety, *Environ. Int.*, 88, pp. 299-309;
3. Miller, P.W., Martens, D.C., Zelazny, L.W. (1986). Effect of sequence in extraction of trace metals from soils. *Soil Science Society of America Journal*, 50 (3), 598–601. <https://doi.org/10.2136/sssaj1986.03615995005000030011x> 2x;
4. Akhalbedashvili L., Todradze G., Kvatahidze R., Loria N., Gagniasvili N., Janashvili N., Jalaghania S., (2023). Content of heavy metals in station areas in some cities in Georgia. *Sciences of Europe*, NO 129, p.48-52.
5. Chao Su, LiQin Jiang, WenJun Zhang. (2014), A review on heavy metal contamination in the soil worldwide: Situation, impact and remediation techniques. *Environmental Skeptics and Critics*, 3(2): 24-38
6. Tessier, A., Campbell, P.G.C. and Bisson, M. (1979) Sequential Extraction Procedure for the Speciation of Particular Trace Elements. *Analytical Chemistry*, 51, 844-851. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ac50043a017>;
7. Raksataya, A.G. Langdon, N.D. Kim, (1996), Assessment of the extent of lead redistribution during sequential extraction by two different methods, *Analytica Chimica Acta*, Volume 332, Issue 1, 10 October Pages 1-14, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0003-2670\(96\)00227-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/0003-2670(96)00227-9)

8. Pinskiy, D.L., Iovcheva, A.D., Minkina, T.M., Bauer, T.V., Nevidomskaya, D.G., Shuvaeva, V.A., Mandzhieva, S. S., Tsitsuashvili, V. S., Burachevskaya, M.V. (2022). Identification of heavy metal compounds in technogenically transformed soils using sequential fractionation, XAFS spectroscopy, and XRD powder diffraction. *Pochvovedenie*, 5, 600–614. (In Russian);
9. Pueyo, M., Mateu, J., Rigol, A., Vidal, M., López-Sánchez, J.F., Rauret, G. (2008). Use of the modified BCR three-step sequential extraction procedure for the study of trace element dynamics in contaminated soils. *Environmental Pollution*, 152 (2), 330–341.
- <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2007.06.020a>;
10. Siromlya, T.I. (2009). About the mobile forms of the compounds of chemical elements in soils. *Sibirskii ekologicheskii zhurnal*, 2, 307–318. (In Russian);
11. Henry Vallius (1999). Anthropogenically derived heavy metals in recent sediments of the Gulf of Finland, Baltic Sea. *Chemosphere*, V. 38, Issue 5, p. 945-962;
12. D.V. Ladonin. (2016), Forms of heavy metals in technogenically polluted soils, Moscow. Abstract for the degree of Doctor of Biological Sciences.